

Development And Validation of Impurity Profiling in Amlodipine Besylate by High Performance Liquid Chromatography

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ABSTRACT

In present study, simple, cost effective, time saving, gradient, accurate and reproducible HPLC analytical technique was developed and validated for the simultaneous quantification of genotoxic and process impurities of Amlodipine Besylate. The method was developed on Agilent HPLC C18 column, with mobile phase of 10 mM Sodium dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate in water adjusted to pH \pm 3.5 with Orthophosphoric acid and 100% Acetonitrile. The flow rate of 1.2 ml per min was maintained and column oven temperature of 15°C. Detection done at 220 (for genotoxic impurities) and 280 nm (for process impurities) using UV detector. The method was validated for specificity, system suitability, Linearity, Precision, LOD, LOQ and Accuracy. Analytical method passed the acceptance criteria of specificity and system suitability. LODs for genotoxic (0.085 ppm and 0.084 ppm) and process (0.754 ppm and 0.6945 ppm) were well within acceptance limit. Similarly, LOQs for genotoxic (0.254 ppm and 0.252 ppm) and process (2.261 ppm and 2.084 ppm) were also well within acceptance limit. Both genotoxic and process impurities showed excellent linearity with R² of 0.999 for each impurity. The precision and accuracy parameters were also found to be well within acceptable limit. The results confirmed that the method is accurate, linear and reliable for the quantitative estimation of impurities in single method at time, cost, manpower and usage of solvents.

Keywords: Amlodipine Besylate, Impurity, Genotoxic impurity, Process impurity, HPLC, Method validation.

INTRODUCTION

Pharmaceutical impurities are often generated during formulation, synthesis, storage, or degradation. These impurities can be very harmful even at trace levels and significantly hamper efficacy, safety, and stability of the finished product [1]. Considering the potential risk of impurities, regulatory agencies like International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) emphasize stringent quality control measures to ensure that the presence of impurities remains within acceptable limits to safeguard patient health. So, ICH has provided guidelines to control the impurities [2, 3]. Among various impurities, genotoxic impurities (GTIs) are of major concern due to the potential to interact with DNA, inducing mutations, and ultimately increasing the risk of cancer. Therefore, it is advisable to continuously monitor, identify, and quantify of all such impurities which now have become a crucial aspect of modern pharmaceutical analysis [4].

Amlodipine besylate is calcium channel blocker, having antihypertensive activity and is widely prescribed alone or in combination for managing hypertension and angina pectoris. Due to its excellent therapeutic results in Indian market, it is greatly prescribed by the physicians [5]. Due to its chronic usage, maintaining high purity levels of the API becomes essential. During synthesis of Amlodipine besylate, several impurities may be introduced, including genotoxic impurities such as 2-Chlorobenzyl monochloride and 1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene, which are derived from chlorinated intermediates. Apart from this, process impurities such as Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 (3-(2-chlorophenyl)-2-{2-[2-(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydroisoindol-2-yl)ethoxy]acetyl} acrylic acid ethyl ester) and Impurity-2 (Ethyl 4-(2-(1,3-Dioxoisoindolin-2-yl)Ethoxy)-3-Oxobutanoate) may originate from incomplete reactions or side reactions

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[6]. Even trace amounts of these impurities could pose significant toxicological hazards, especially considering the long-term therapy nature of the medication [7]. Presence of genotoxic contaminants necessitates ultra-sensitive measurement to fulfill ICH M7 regulatory criteria. Current analytical techniques require separate approaches for GTIs and process impurities, which is ineffective and resource intensive. Monitoring can be made easier, solvent consumption can be decreased, analysis time can be reduced, and laboratory productivity can be increased using a single certified HPLC method. The regulatory bodies have set very stringent requirements and controls on the levels of impurities, especially for GTIs. The concentrations of such impurities typically require below parts per million (ppm) as per the regulatory guidelines [8, 9]. According to ICH M7 guideline, the analytical tool should detect and quantify the impurities at extremely low concentrations with accuracy and specificity [10]. Previously, different analytical techniques were generally applied for GTIs and for process-related impurities, which increases analytical effort, time, expense, and consumption of organic solvents. Moreover, frequent analysis might hamper efficiency within pharmaceutical quality control laboratories [11].

HPLC has proved as a versatile, authentic and widely accepted analytical technique for estimation and quantification of impurity profiling due to its excellent accuracy, reproducibility, resolution and compatibility with various drugs [12]. Development of single integrated HPLC method that can effectively separate and quantify the process and genotoxic impurities can help to enhance analytical efficiency as well as minimize the resources, time and energy [13, 14]. In detailed impurity profiling of Amlodipine besylate can help to understand the degradation pathways, quality consistency and process robustness. Moreover, the validated analytical method supports the lifecycle management of the drug and ensures regulatory compliance [15].

Based on the regulatory, scientific and practical considerations, the present research was undertaken to

develop and validate simple, new, accurate and cost effective HPLC analytical method for estimation of two process and two genotoxic impurities in Amlodipine besylate. The proposed method offers an integrated solution that eliminates the need for multiple analytical procedures, thereby enhancing productivity and reducing analytical costs within pharmaceutical quality control environments.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals:

Amlodipine Besylate was obtained as gift sample from Ajanta Pharma, Mumbai. 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride, 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl, Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 were brought from different local suppliers. Sodium dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate was purchased from Merck, Acetonitrile was obtained from Honeywell, Orthophosphoric acid was purchased from Rankem.

Instrumentation and Chromatographic conditions

HPLC system (Agilent) with ASCENTIS EXPRESS ES-CN C18 column (150mm x 4.6mm x 2.7 μ m) with UV-visible detector was employed in gradient mode to accomplish chromatographic separation. The mobile phase contained 10 mM Sodium dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate in water adjusted to pH \pm 3.5 with Orthophosphoric acid (Mobile phase A) and 100% Acetonitrile (Mobile phase B). It was degassed, sonicated and operated on gradient mode for run time of 20 min. 5 μ l of sample was injected at a flow rate of 1.2 ml/min into the HPLC. During analysis, Column oven temperature and Autosampler temperature was kept at 15°C and 5°C respectively.

Detection of 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride and 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene was performed at 220 nm while Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and Impurity-2 at 280 nm. Following gradient program was used and optimized during development and validation (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Gradient Program

Time (mins)	Solution A (%)	Solution B (%)
0.0	55	45
3.0	55	45
10.0	20	80
15.0	20	80
15.1	55	45
20.0	55	45

Solution preparation:**Stock solution of 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride :**

20.0 mg of 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride std weighed accurately and added into 20 ml volumetric flask containing about 5ml of diluent (5.0ml of water in 100ml Acetonitrile). The solution was mixed thoroughly and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Stock solution of 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene:

20.0 mg of 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene stand was weighed accurately into 20ml volumetric flask containing about 5ml of diluent. The solution was mixed thoroughly and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Stock solution of Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1:

30.0 mg of Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 std was weighed accurately into 20ml volumetric flask containing about 5ml of diluent. The solution was mixed thoroughly and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Stock solution of Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2:

20.0 mg of Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2 std was weighed accurately into 20 ml volumetric flask containing about 5ml of diluent. The solution was mixed thoroughly and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Standard stock solution (SSS):

0.85 ml stock solution for 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride and stock solution for 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene and 7.5 ml each of stock solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and

stock solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2 was transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask containing 30 ml of diluent and diluted to volume with diluent and mixed.

Standard solution:

1.0 ml of SSS was transferred into 10 ml of volumetric flask containing about 3 ml of diluent and diluted up to the mark with diluent and mixed properly.

Sample solution:

About 75 mg of sample was weighed accurately and transferred into 10 ml of volumetric flask and Add 7.0 ml of diluent was added. The resulting solution was sonicated to dissolve, cool and diluted up to the mark with diluent and mixed properly.

Method Validation [12]**Specificity & system suitability:**

Specificity & system suitability study was performed by injecting separately 5.0 µl of Blank, Standard solution, Blank, Sample solution, Spiked sample solution, Identification solution (ID solutions) and Blank into the chromatographic system. The major peak area responses were recorded and assessed to ensure compliance with system suitability requirements. Identification solutions and Spiked sample solution were prepared as follows.

Identification solution for 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride:

Accurately weighed 20.0 mg of 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride standard was added into 20 ml volumetric flask containing about 5ml of diluent. This solution was thoroughly mixed and diluted up to the

mark with diluent. Approx 0.85 ml of prepared solution was made up to 100 ml with diluent and mixed well, followed by dilution of 1.0 ml to 10 ml diluent and mixed thoroughly.

Identification solution for 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene:

Accurately weighed 20.0 mg of 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene standard was added into 20 ml volumetric flask containing about 5ml of diluent. This solution was thoroughly mixed and diluted up to the mark with diluent. Approx 0.85 ml of prepared solution was made up to 100 ml with diluent and mixed well, followed by dilution of 1.0 ml to 10 ml diluent and mixed thoroughly.

Identification solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1:

Accurately weighed 30.0 mg of Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 standard was added into 20 ml volumetric flask containing about 5ml of diluent. This solution was mixed thoroughly and diluted up to the mark with diluent. Approx 7.5 ml of prepared solution was made up to 100 ml with diluent and mixed well, followed by dilution of 1.0 ml to 10 ml diluent and mixed thoroughly.

Identification solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2:

Accurately weighed 20.0 mg of Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2 standard was added into 20 ml volumetric flask containing about 5ml of diluent. This solution was mixed thoroughly and diluted up to the mark with diluent. Approx 7.5 ml of prepared solution was made up to 100 ml with diluent and mixed well, followed by dilution of 1.0 ml to 10 ml diluent and mixed thoroughly.

Spiked sample solution:

75 mg of the sample was weighed accurately into a 10 mL volumetric flask. After adding 7.0 mL of diluent, the solution was sonicated to dissolve, cooled, then 1.0 mL of SSS A was added, and the volume was completed with diluent.

Limit of detection (LOD):

LOD stock solution:

0.85 ml each of stock solution for 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride and stock solution for 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene and 7.5 ml each of stock solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and stock solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2 was added into 100 ml volumetric flask containing approx 30 ml of diluent and diluted to volume with diluent and mixed. 5.0 µl of blank solution and LOD preparation were injected in three replicates.

Limit of quantitation (LOQ):

LOQ stock solution:

0.85 ml each of stock solution for 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride and stock solution for 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene and 7.5 ml each of stock solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and stock solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2 was added into 100 ml volumetric flask containing approx. 30 ml of diluent and diluted to volume with diluent and mixed. 5.0 µl of blank solution and LOQ preparation were injected in three replicates.

Linearity:

Linearity stock solution:

0.85 ml each of stock solution for 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride and stock solution for 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene and 7.5 ml each of stock solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and stock solution for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2 was added into 100 ml volumetric flask containing approx. 30 ml of diluent and diluted to volume with diluent and mixed. 5.0 µl each of LIN-I and LIN-V in 6 replicates and LIN-II, LIN-III, LIN-IV was injected in duplicate.

Precision:

5.0 µl of Blank, Standard solution Blank, Sample solution (1, 2...6) were injected into the chromatographic system. The major peak area responses were recorded and assessed to confirm compliance with system suitability requirements.

Accuracy:

5.0 µl of Blank, Standard solution, Blank, Accuracy level solution, and Blank were injected separately into the chromatographic system. The major peak area responses were recorded and assessed to confirm compliance with system suitability requirements. Accuracy level solutions were prepared as follows.

Accuracy Level-1 solution (Accuracy LOQ solution):

Approx 75 mg of sample was weighed accurately into 10 ml of volumetric flask. To this, 7.0 ml of diluent was added and followed by sonication to dissolve it completely. Then, 0.3 ml of SSS A was added and volume was made up to the mark with diluent.

Accuracy Level-2 solution (Accuracy 50% solution):

Approx 75 mg of sample was weighed accurately into 10 ml of volumetric flask. To this, 7.0 ml of diluent was added and followed by sonication to dissolve it completely. Then, 0.5 ml of SSS A was added and volume was made up to the mark with diluent.

Accuracy Level-3 solution (Accuracy 100% solution):

Approx 75 mg of sample was weighed accurately into 10 ml of volumetric flask. To this, 7.0 ml of diluent was added and followed by sonication to dissolve it completely. Then, 1 ml of SSS A was added and volume was made up to the mark with diluent.

Accuracy Level-4 solution (Accuracy 150% solution):

Approx 75 mg of sample was weighed accurately into 10 ml of volumetric flask. To this, 7.0 ml of diluent

was added and followed by sonication to dissolve it completely. Then, 1.5 ml of SSS A was added and volume was made up to the mark with diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Mobile phase selection and optimization

Initial very few trials were conducted in isocratic mode using buffer: ACN (60:40) showed the RT of about 9 mins for 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride, RT of 10 min for 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene, RT of 10 min for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and RT of 6 for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2. Further few trials were performed to minimize the RT of all impurities. None of the trials were successful to elute all four impurities at minimum RT in isocratic mode. To resolve this problem, gradient program was introduced in which RT of all four impurities was drastically minimized. RT of about 6 mins for 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride, RT of 7 min for 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene, RT of 7.5 min for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and RT of 2.9 for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2 was observed in gradient mode program as reported in **Table 1**. Thereafter, a short, cost effective, accurate gradient elution method was developed, demonstrating improved precision.

Specificity and system suitability:

The specificity of the developed analytical method was assessed, and it was found that the blank solutions and ID solutions did not show any interference at the retention time of respective peaks (**Figure 1 and 2**). All four impurity peaks were well identified and separated from each other.

Figure 1: Chromatogram of Blank, 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride and 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene

Figure 2: Chromatogram of Blank, Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2

In case of STD solution, the RSD for the peak area response of respective impurities for replicate injections was not more than 5.0 % each and RSD for

RT of respective impurities for replicate injections of STD solution was not more than 1.0%. The results are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Summary of %RSD of RT and area of std solution

Impurity	1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene		2-Chloro benzyl monochloride		Amlodipine Besylate Imp-1		Amlodipine Besylate Imp-2	
	RT	Area	RT	Area	RT	Area	RT	Area
Mean	7.01	7595.67	5.95	9656.67	1259.77	43403.50	2.94	6523.33
SD	0.00	52.56	0.00	60.26	3067.36	94.81	0.00	1283.17
% RSD	0.03	0.69	0.04	0.62	243.49	0.22	0.08	19.67

System suitability is a crucial component of chromatography technique validation, which aims to confirm that the system will yield consistent and dependable results prior to sample analysis [17]. The system suitability study ensured that the developed chromatographic system is suitable for the estimation of the impurities. The RT for 2-Chloro Benzyl Monochloride was found to be 6 min, for 1-Chloro-2-Dichloromethyl Benzene was 7 min, for Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-I and II was 7.5 and 2.9 respectively. The RT of all impurities provided the reliability of the analytes and their consistency was validated by calculating %RSD which was not more than 1.0% which meet the acceptance criteria. Also, %RSD for the peak area were also found within acceptance criteria of not more than 5.0 %. Moreover, the chromatogram demonstrated a well-defined and sharp peak for all impurities, with no excessive broadening, ensuring accurate quantification. Overall, this investigation confirmed that the system complies to the set requirements for impurity analysis, suggesting its suitability for reliable and consistent analytical performance.

Limit of detection (LOD):

The LOD study evaluated the minimum detectable concentrations of genotoxic impurities and process impurities using developed method. As per **table 2** it was found that the developed method demonstrated excellent sensitivity across all impurities. In case of genotoxic impurities, LOD levels were found to be 0.085 ppm and 0.084 ppm with signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios of 15 and 23 respectively which clearly confirmed the analytical methods reliable detectability well above the standard acceptance criterion of $S/N \geq 3$. On the other hand, process impurities were also detected at very trace concentrations with LODs of 0.754 ppm and 0.6945 ppm with corresponding S/N ratios of 115 and 19 demonstrating excellent and very clear analytical responses at very trace levels. Moreover, the calculated ppm and % w.r.t. samples also confirmed that the developed analytical method can efficiently detect the impurities at extremely low concentrations, meeting regulatory expectations for sensitive impurity profiling. Overall, the LOD results demonstrate that the method provides robust, sensitive, and dependable detection of genotoxic and process-related impurities in Amlodipine Besylate, ensuring suitability for routine quality control and regulatory compliance.

Table 2: Summary of Concentration of Impurity standards in LOD level

1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene			2-Chloro benzyl monochloride			Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1			Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2		
ppm	ppm w.r.t Sample	% w.r.t Sample	ppm	ppm w.r.t Sample	% w.r.t Sample	ppm	ppm w.r.t Sample	% w.r.t Sample	ppm	ppm w.r.t Sample	% w.r.t Sample
0.085	11.3	0.00113	0.084	11.2	0.00112	0.754	100.5	0.01005	0.6945	92.6	0.00926
S/N Ratio	15		23			115			19		

Limit of quantification (LOQ):

The LOQ study was performed to detect the lowest concentration of impurities that can be quantified using the developed analytical method. As per **table 3** it was found that the developed method demonstrated excellent quantification of all impurities. The developed analytical method showed excellent and strong analytical performance, with LOQ concentrations of 0.254 ppm and 0.252 ppm for the two genotoxic impurities, with high S/N ratios of 43 and 67, respectively, indicating excellent detectability and quantification capability. On the other hand, the process impurities also showed LOQ concentrations

of 2.261 ppm and 2.084 ppm with exceptionally high S/N ratios of 347 and 58, confirming excellent detectability. Moreover, the %RSD of peak areas for all impurities were found to be well within acceptable limits (should not be more than 5.0 %), ranging from 0.3% to 4.1%, indicating accurate, reproducible and precise quantification at extremely lower concentrations. These observations clearly confirmed that the developed analytical method can quantify the both genotoxic and process-related impurities at trace levels, making it suitable for routine quality control and ensuring regulatory compliance for impurity profiling in Amlodipine Besylate.

Table 3: Summary of Concentration of Impurity standards in LOQ level

1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene			2-Chloro benzyl monochloride			Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1			Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2		
ppm	ppm w.r.t Sample	% w.r.t Sample	ppm	ppm w.r.t Sample	% w.r.t Sample	ppm	ppm w.r.t Sample	% w.r.t Sample	ppm	ppm w.r.t Sample	% w.r.t Sample
0.254	33.9	0.00339	0.252	33.6	0.00336	2.261	301.5	0.03015	2.084	277.8	0.02778
S/N Ratio	43		67			347			58		
% RSD of area	2.1		4.1			0.3			1.4		

Linearity:

This study was conducted at five different concentration levels for all four impurities as summarized in **Table 4 and 5** to check the

proportional relation between the concentration of impurity and peak area. Both genotoxic and process impurities showed excellent linearity with R^2 of 0.999 for each impurity (**Table 4 and Figure 3**) satisfying acceptance criteria of NLT 0.999.

Figure 3: Linearity plots of impurities

It has also been observed that the % Y intercept for all four impurities was ranged between -0.28 to 0.8 demonstrating calibration curves adequately pass near the origin. satisfying the acceptance criteria of ± 3.0

Table 4: Linearity study with concentration and area of impurities

2-Chloro benzyl monochloride		1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene		Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1		Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2	
Conc.	Area	Conc.	Area	Conc.	Area	Conc.	Area
33.9	2984	33.6	2278	0.03	13121	0.03	1765
56.4	4891	55.9	3877	0.05	21653	0.05	2910
112.9	9683	111.9	7539	0.10	43742	0.09	5958
135.5	11674	134.2	9198	0.12	52269	0.11	6910
169.3	14646	167.8	11366	0.15	65655	0.14	8697
Regression	0.999	Regression	0.999	Regression	0.999	Regression	0.999
%Y intercept	0.4	%Y intercept	0.54	% Y intercept	-0.28	% Y intercept	0.8

Moreover, the % RSD values for peak area at lowest (LIN-I) and highest (LIN-V) levels were found to be in the range of 0.0% to 4.1% (Table 5) satisfying the acceptance criteria of NMT 5.0%. These observations and results confirmed that the developed analytical

method is linear, precise and reproducible across studied concentration ranges of the impurities. Hence, the method reliably quantifies genotoxic and process-related impurities in Amlodipine Besylate with strong linearity performance suitable for regulatory-compliant impurity profiling.

Table 5: % RSD of peak area response of impurities

2-Chloro benzyl monochloride					
Sr. No	Lin-I	Lin-II	Lin-III	Lin-IV	Lin-V
Mean	2983.7	4891.0	9683.0	11674.0	14646.2
SD	62.3	4.2	199.4	137.2	81.6
%RSD	2.1	0.1	2.1	1.2	0.6
1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene					
Mean	2278.33	3876.50	7538.50	9197.50	11365.50
SD	93.6	74.2	3.5	47.4	78.4
%RSD	4.1	1.9	0.0	0.5	0.7
Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1					
Mean	13121.17	21652.50	43741.50	52269.00	65655.33
SD	43.1	61.5	37.5	101.8	70.7
%RSD	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.1
Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2					
Mean	1765.33	2910.00	5958.00	6909.50	8696.50
SD	24.7	38.2	162.6	40.3	51.0
%RSD	1.4	1.3	2.7	0.6	0.6

Precision:

Precision was studied by injecting replicate std solutions of the impurities and it has been observed that the developed analytical method demonstrated

excellent repeatability for RT and peak area as summarized in Table 6. % RSD of RT for all impurities was found extremely low ranging between 0.00% to 0.08% satisfying the acceptance criteria (NMT 1%). Similar observation was noted for peak

area with %RSD between 0.22% and 19.67% satisfying the acceptance criteria (NMT 5%) except Impurity 2. Overall, the collected data demonstrated that the developed method has enough accuracy, with

steady RT and similar peak area responses throughout multiple injections, assuring the repeatability and dependability of impurity measurement during routine analysis.

Table 6: % RSD of peak area and RT response of impurities

Sr. No	RT	Area
1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene		
Mean	7.01	7595.67
SD	0.00	52.56
%RSD	0.03	0.69
2-Chloro benzyl monochloride		
Mean	5.95	9656.67
SD	0.00	60.26
%RSD	0.04	0.62
Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1		
Mean	1259.77	43403.50
SD	3067.36	94.81
%RSD	243.49	0.22
Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2		
Mean	2.94	6523.33
SD	0.00	1283.17
%RSD	0.08	19.67

Accuracy:

In accuracy study % recovery of all impurities was studied at four levels as mentioned in method section to evaluate the trueness of the method. It has been observed that % recovery values of all impurities were well within acceptance criteria. At the LOQ level, recoveries for all impurities ranged from 95.0% to 100.1%, meeting the required range of 70–130%, confirming reliable quantification even at very low concentrations. Moreover, at 2-4 levels, the % recoveries were found between 94.9% and 103.1%, satisfying the acceptance criteria of 80–120%. Also, the %RSD for RT was found below 1% and for peak

area it was consistently below 5% satisfying the acceptance criteria.

Additionally, precision parameters evaluated during accuracy (as shown by the %RSD values of RT and peak area in Table 7) were all within acceptable limits, with %RSD for retention time consistently below 0.10% and %RSD for peak area well below the 5.0% limit for each impurity (Table 8). These results collectively confirm that the method provides accurate and precise recovery for genotoxic impurities and process impurities across the entire tested concentration range, demonstrating its suitability for quantitative impurity assessment in routine quality control.

Table 7: % accuracy study results for impurities

Impurity	2-Chloro benzyl monochloride	1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene	Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1	Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2
Accuracy levels	% Accuracy	% Accuracy	% Accuracy	% Accuracy
Level-1 (LOQ)	95.0	100.1	99.7	99.5

Level-2 (50%)	94.9	100.8	96.5	97.5
Level-3 (100%)	97.3	103.1	95.8	102.4
Level-4 (150%)	97.0	102.7	98.3	99.3

Table 8: % RSD of peak area and RT response of impurities

Sr. No	RT	Area
1-Chloro-2-dichloromethyl benzene		
Mean	7.03	7352.33
SD	0.00	57.25
%RSD	0.03	0.78
2-Chloro benzyl monochloride		
Mean	5.97	9717.67
SD	0.00	87.39
%RSD	0.08	0.90
Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1		
Mean	7.53	42605.50
SD	0.00	59.19
%RSD	0.05	0.14
Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2		
Mean	2.95	5679.67
SD	0.00	33.16
%RSD	0.06	0.58

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully developed and validated accurate, precise analytical method for the simultaneous estimation of genotoxic (2-Chloro benzyl monochloride and 1-chloro-2-Dichloromethyl benzene) and process impurities (Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-1 and Amlodipine Besylate Impurity-2). This developed analytical method demonstrated excellent linearity, accuracy and capable of detecting and quantifying the impurities at very trace concentrations. Based on the validation the method can be proposed for routine quality control for release of commercial batches. The method can quantify the genotoxic and process impurities simultaneously in single method rather than two different methods at minimum time, cost, manpower and usage of solvents.

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